

Spectrophotometric Studies on Some 3-Pyridylazo Dyes

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Evaluation of the dissociation constants of the acid groups of some 3-pyridylazo dyes is reported. The pK values of the deprotonation constant of the pyridyl nitrogen atom and the ionisation of hydroxyl group were determined from the variation of absorbance with pH . The effect of pH on the absorption spectra of the dyes under investigation is discussed. The spectra reveal the presence of two equilibria indicating the existence of two ionisation steps.

DURING the past 20 years or so the application of pyridylazo compounds in chemical analysis has been studied extensively¹⁻⁵. However, the literature referring to the use of 3-pyridylazo dyes in analytical chemistry is very limited, although the diazotization of 3-aminopyridine is performed easily in contrast to 2- or 4-aminopyridine. Further investigations are, therefore, required to throw more light on the nature of such reagents. For this purpose, the following azo dyes (I_{a-k}), derived from 3-aminopyridine, were prepared and their acid-base properties were investigated.

R = phenol (I_a), *o*-cresol (I_b), *m*-cresol (I_c), *p*-cresol (I_d), 1-naphthol (I_e), 2-naphthol (I_f), 1-OH, 4-SO₃H naphthalene (I_g), 2-OH, 6-SO₃H-naphthalene (I_h), 2-OH, 3,6-SO₃H-naphthalene (I_i), 1,8-OH, 3,6-SO₃H-naphthalene (I_j), 8-OH-quinoline (I_k).

Experimental

The pyridylazo dyes used in this investigation were prepared by diazotization of 3-aminopyridine in the usual way as recommended by Vogel⁶. The resulting diazonium salt was coupled with phenol⁷, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresol, 1-, and 2-naphthol⁸, Nevile Winther's acid (N.W.)⁹, Schaffer acid, R-acid and 8-hydroxyquinoline in sodium hydroxide medium. The coupling was in sodium carbonate medium in case of chromotropic acid¹⁰. The resulting azo dyes were recrystallized by recommended methods or applying appropriate solvents. The 0.001 M dye solutions were prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed dye in appropriate volume of deionized water or ethyl alcohol. Universal buffer solutions covering pH values from 2.0 to 12.0 were prepared as recommended by Britton¹¹, and checked by means of a Corning pH meter 113, accurate to ± 0.01 pH unit. The pK values of the strong sulphonic groups were determined potentiometrically applying the relation $pH = pK - \log(\text{acid})/(\text{salt})$.

The different methods applied for the determination of pK values of the OH- and $\text{N}^+\text{-H}$ groups were :

1. The half height method¹², for which the pK is equal to the pH at half height of the absorbance- pH curve.
2. The modified limiting absorbance method¹³ using the relation :

$$pH = pK + \log \gamma' + \log \frac{A - A_{\min}}{A_1 - A}$$

where A_1 = limiting absorbance value on the A - pH curve,

A_{\min} = minimum absorbance value on the A - pH curve,

A = absorbance at a given pH and

γ' = activity coefficient term.

3. The Colleter¹⁴ method as modified for the acid-base equilibria using the relation :

$$K = \frac{C_{H_2^+} - MC_{H_3^+}}{M - 1}$$

$$\text{where } M = \left(\frac{A_3 - A_1}{A_2 - A_1} \right) \left(\frac{C_{H_2^+} - C_{H_3^+}}{C_{H_2^+} - C_{H_3^+}} \right)$$

where A_1 , A_2 and A_3 are absorbance values at three different H^+ concentrations C_{H_1} , C_{H_2} and C_{H_3} .

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of 3-pyridylazo compounds are characterised by a strong band in the visible region, which is assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the azo group influenced by charge transfer through the molecule. In acid medium, this band is located in the range 359-476 nm (Table I) which is attributed to absorption of the protonated species existing in acidic solutions. In alkaline solutions, this band is red shifted to longer wavelength absorbing maximally in the 410-500 nm region. This band is due to absorption of the anionic form predominating in the alkaline solutions.

TABLE 1—COLLECTIVE DATA OF pK VALUES FOR IONISATION STEPS OF 3-PYRIDYLAZO DYES

No.	Cat.	λ_{nm} Neu	Ani	pK_b	pK_{a_1}	pK_{a_2}	$-\Delta G_D^0$	$-\Delta G_{a_1}^0$	$-\Delta G_{a_2}^0$
Ia	359	347	425	3.54	7.55	—	4.90	10.46	—
Ib	368	353	443	3.63	7.91	—	5.03	10.96	—
Ic	370	353	410	3.69	8.01	—	5.11	11.09	—
Id	404	380	480	3.23	8.86	—	4.47	12.27	—
Ie	430	445	500	4.32	7.79	—	5.98	10.79	—
If	452	455	440	3.81	10.33	—	5.28	14.31	—
Ig	462	380	490	4.01	7.41	—	5.55	10.26	—
Ih	449	462	462	4.46	9.39	—	6.17	13.00	—
Ii	460	473	473	3.98	9.69	—	5.51	13.41	—
Ij	476	490	460, 494	3.57	7.19, 10.07	—	4.94	9.95	13.94
Ik	398	410	485	3.89	8.02	—	5.39	11.11	—

Cat = cationic, Neu = neutral, Ani = anionic.
 pK_b = Protonation constant.
 pK_a = Ionisation constant.

The variation of absorbance with pH of the buffer solutions is used successfully for the determination of both the protonation and the ionisation constants of the pyridyl nitrogen and the hydroxyl groups applying the above mentioned methods. The absorbance- pH curves for all compounds except (Ij) exhibit two inflections confirming the presence of two ionization steps (3 in case of Ij).

The absorption spectra of 3-pyridylazo dyes in buffer solutions reveal the existence of two equilibria and hence two steps of ionisation. The absorption spectra evidently show the existence of an equilibrium in acid solutions between cationic species and the non-charged species, while the other one, predominating in alkaline solutions, is mainly between neutral and anionic species. Thus, the overall equilibrium may be represented as :

The presence of such two ionisation steps is revealed by the presence of an isobestic point over a certain pH range below or above which deviation is observed.

In case of 2-(3-pyridylazo)-chromotropic acid (Ij), three steps of ionisations are detected indicating that the two naphthalenic hydroxyl groups are ionisable. It is to be mentioned here that the ionisation of the sulphonic acid groups in compounds Ig, Ih, Ii and Ij causes no spectral change, which is in harmony with previous studies⁴.

Considering the data given in Table 1 the following points can be deduced :

(a) The phenyl azo compound is the most acidic one with respect to the ionisation of the OH group.

(b) The introduction of the methyl group in 2 or 3 position (Ib and Ic) increases the pK value. This is due to the inductive effect of such group which increases the charge density on the phenyl ring, opposing the charge transfer from the OH group, which causes stronger bonding of the proton to the oxygen atom.

(c) The change in the position of the OH group from 4 to 2 position (Id) increases the pK value by 0.95 and 0.85 pK units with respect to compounds Ib and Ic. Such increases are equivalent to 1.31 or 1.18 K.cal/mole which lies in the range of the hydrogen bond formation energy.

(d) On substituting the naphthyl or quinoline ring instead of the phenyl one (Ia and Ie or Ik), a slight increase in the pK value is observed which may be attributed to greater participation of the hydrazone form in the case of Ie which retards the ionisation of the naphthalenic OH group.

(e) Comparing compounds (Ie) and (If), it is clear that (If) is less acidic than (Ie) and this may be ascribed to the formation of strong intramolecular hydrogen bond in case of (If) and greater participation of the hydrazone tautomer.

(f) The high acidity character of the naphthalenic OH group in compound (Ig) may be attributed to the presence of the strong electron withdrawing sulphonic acid group in p -position to the OH group which decreases the extent of hydrogen bond formation. The effect of the sulphonic acid group in $meta$ (6) position (Ih) and 3,6 position (Ij) is less than if it was present in $para$ position (Ig).

(g) The increase in maximum absorption of the main band position in the azo compounds by introducing the naphthyl ring instead of the phenyl ring is due to increasing the extent of the π -system of the molecule.

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